

Gender Disparities in Literacy in Rural Uttar Pradesh: Trends and Patterns of Literacy from 1991 to 2011

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Nivedita Paul

Assistant Professor
Geography And Population
Studies
Marwari College, Ranchi
University
RanchiJharkhand, India

Abstract

Gender disparity in Literacy is a crucial measure of development that shows how the society is performing in terms of gender. Using Census data 2011 and Kundu and Rao (1986) disparity Index, Gender disparity is calculated for Rural Uttar Pradesh. Uttar Pradesh being a large state shows disparities in various aspects of Geography and development. Rural areas of Uttar Pradesh facing the backlash of out-migration and lower development levels are prone to more disparities. While progress is reflected in the steady decline of the Gender Disparity Index from 0.52 in 1991 to 0.23 in 2011 in Uttar Pradesh, the district level analysis of disparity shows Gender disparity in rural literacy is widespread and significant across Uttar Pradesh where most districts fall in the moderate to high disparity categories (0.21–0.26), indicating a persistent gap between male and female literacy. The district-level analysis of literacy growth indicates that the most rapid improvements occurred during 1991–2001 when compared to 2001–2011. SC literacy disparity shows moderate variation across districts when compared to ST disadvantage that is highly spatially uneven, unlike SC disparity.

Keywords

Gender, Disparity, Literacy, Rural, Uttar Pradesh.

Introduction

Literacy is a critical indicator of human development, reflecting both the social and economic progress of a region. As defined by the Census of India, a literate person is one who can read and write with understanding in any language, regardless of formal educational attainment. Besides from 1991 census, all children of age 6 years or less are treated as illiterates even though they may be going to school and can read and write a few odd words. Beyond improving individual opportunities for education and employment, literacy enhances human capital and facilitates wider participation in society.

Although India has witnessed notable improvements in literacy over the past few decades, sharp disparities remain across regions and social groups. Rural literacy is particularly significant, as nearly 70 percent of India's population resides in villages where socio-economic constraints often restrict access to education. Despite modernization, urbanization, and government initiatives, inequalities persist by gender, caste, tribe, and religion. In rural areas, gender disparities are especially pronounced, with women experiencing limited educational opportunities and lower literacy outcomes. Besides, large scale urbanization from the rural areas of UP to the urban areas, render the rural areas with comparatively less educated population.

Uttar Pradesh, India's most populous state, presents a striking example of such inequalities. Historically, the northern hill districts had comparatively higher literacy levels, but these were carved out to form Uttarakhand in 2000. Within the current boundaries of Uttar Pradesh, wide district-level variations in literacy continue to exist, accompanied by persistent gaps between men and women and significant disadvantages faced by Scheduled Castes, Scheduled Tribes, and Muslim communities. Examining these patterns is crucial for understanding the socio-spatial dimensions of literacy and for identifying policy directions to reduce disparities in the state. Disparity (in rural areas) can be seen in terms of different groups like male-female, among the Scheduled castes and Scheduled tribes, among different religious groups, etc. "Disparity between two groups in their possession of a particular property (in this case literacy) is measured by the logarithm of the odds ratio, that is, the ratio of the odds that any member of one group has the property to the odds that any member of the other group does." The paper, however, serves into the literacy patterns of rural areas of Uttar Pradesh thereby bringing the focus to the large scale out-migration from the rural areas, inaccessibility and uneven pattern of development in the rural areas of Uttar Pradesh.

Objective of study

1. The study aims to examine the disparities in literacy across districts of Uttar Pradesh over the period till 2011.
2. To analyse temporal trends in literacy at the district level (rural).
3. To measure male–female disparity in literacy and variations among different social groups, particularly Scheduled Castes (SCs) and Scheduled Tribes (STs).

Review of Literature

Literacy has long been recognized as a fundamental indicator of human development, closely linked with economic growth, social transformation, and political empowerment. Sen's (1999) capability approach conceptualizes education as a basic freedom that

enhances individuals' ability to participate meaningfully in society. In the Indian context, improvements in literacy have been central to development planning, yet the progress has slow (Dreze & Sen, 2013).

The rural dimension of literacy is particularly important to be studied, as nearly two-thirds of India's population resides in villages. Chandna (2002) noted that rural literacy is shaped by factors such as agricultural dependency, poverty, availability of schools, and infrastructural accessibility. Kundu (2011) further linked low rural literacy to patterns of out-migration, informal employment, and limited access to social services, suggesting that educational deprivation both causes and reinforces economic marginalization. The Kerala model of development also states that women empowerment in terms of better education facilities is as important as expanding physical facilities and family planning programmes (Susuman et al, 2014)

Disparity at the national level shows that gender disparity in literacy increased continuously from 1981, but decreasing trends after that. Rajasthan shows the highest gender disparity while Meghalaya shows the lowest gender disparity for both rural and urban areas. While literacy and gender disparity are inversely related, while gender disparity in rural areas is more than urban areas (Katiyar, 2016). Uttar Pradesh, being India's most populous state, occupies a critical position in discussions of educational inequality. Singh and Sharma (2010) highlighted significant district-level variations in literacy within the state, pointing to a pronounced west-east divide, with western districts outperforming eastern Uttar Pradesh and Bundelkhand. Narain and Singh (2017) similarly emphasized that uneven development, historical neglect, and weak governance structures have contributed to persistent regional inequalities in Uttar Pradesh, particularly in education and health outcomes.

Methodologically, studies measuring literacy inequality have employed a variety of indices. Sopher (1974) proposed an index of disparity to quantify inequalities between two groups, later refined by Kundu and Rao (1986) for application to Indian literacy data. Their modified index has been widely used in geographical and demographic studies to assess gender and social disparities in education across states and districts, providing a robust quantitative basis for spatial comparison. Female literacy is important as it is a force multiplier for the social development of a country. Studies based on Gender disparity in literacy and work participation rate show the relationship between literacy rate and work participation. Therefore, gender disparity in literacy acts as a significant parameter in understanding the overall development of the state (Modal et al, 2025).

Despite the rich body of literature on literacy and educational inequality in India, relatively few studies adopt a district-level spatial approach focusing specifically on rural Uttar Pradesh. Most analyses either examine national patterns or rely on state-level aggregates, thereby masking intra-state variations. The present study seeks to address this gap by analysing rural literacy disparities in Uttar Pradesh from 1991 to 2011, with a focus on gender and social inequalities at the district level. By integrating temporal trends, spatial patterns, and disparity measures, the study contributes to a more nuanced understanding of how educational inequalities persist and transform within one of India's most demographically and politically significant states.

Methodology

Research Questions

What are the spatial patterns of gender disparities in literacy across districts of Uttar Pradesh?

What are the trends in literacy across the districts?

Study Area

The map of study area represents the districts of Uttar Pradesh.

Source: Census, 2011

Dataset	Source	Year(s)
Literacy (Male & Female)	Primary Census Abstracts	1991, 2001, 2011
Scheduled Caste and Tribe Population	Census of India	2011

Methodology

The analysis combines descriptive statistics, disparity measures, and spatial comparison to study literacy variations across districts of Uttar Pradesh.

Growth Rate of Literacy-Literacy growth was calculated by subtracting the literacy rate of the previous decade from that of the subsequent decade (1991–2001, 2001–2011).

Disparity Measurement-Gender and social group disparities in literacy were estimated using Kundu and Rao (1986) which is a modified version of Sopher’s Index of Disparity (1974). The formula of disparity calculation is as follows:

$$DI = \log (X2/X1) + \log \{ (Q-X1) / (Q-X2) \}$$

where X2 > X1, Q=200 and

DI=Disparity Index

X2=Male Literacy rate

X1=Female Literacy rate

Result and Discussion

There is a substantial and consistent rise in total literacy across the two decades: From 36.66% in 1991 to 53.68% in 2001, further increasing to 65.46% in 2011. This indicates significant progress in educational expansion and access over time. Male literacy shows steady improvement from 52.05% (1991) to 68.01% (2001) and 76.33% (2011). While male literacy was already relatively high in 1991, gains continued, especially during 1991–2001. Female literacy increased more rapidly than male literacy, particularly after 1991. It increased from 19.02% (1991) to 37.74% (2001) and 53.65% (2011). The absolute increase of over 34 percentage between 1991 and 2011 highlights focused policy efforts toward female education. Also, the sharp decline in Gender Disparity Index over time from 0.52 (1991) to 0.35 (2001) and 0.23 (2011) reflects a narrowing gender gap in literacy, primarily driven by faster gains in female literacy relative to male literacy. However, despite notable gains in female literacy, a measurable gender gap persists.

Trends in Literacy across districts of Uttar Pradesh

Decadal increase in Literacy					
District	1991-2001	2001-2011	District	1991-2001	2001-2011
Agra	16.6	13.3	Jaunpur	17.9	12.1
Aligarh	17.9	4.5	Jhansi	16.4	12.7
Allahabad	15.9	13.8	Kanpur	16.1	9.0
Azamgarh	18.1	14.6	Kanpur Dehat	15.7	9.5
Badaun	42.6	-13.7	Lakhimpur Kheri	19.5	13.0
Bahraich	22.9	1.9	Lalitpur	18.4	15.6
Ballia	-10.0	38.2	Lucknow	18.7	13.9
Banda	22.7	9.3	Maharajganj	17.9	16.7
Barabanki	13.5	18.8	Mainpuri	15.6	11.9
Bareilly	26.2	5.0	Mathura	16.9	10.9
Basti	19.6	12.8	Mau	19.7	11.8
Bijnor	-3.9	33.8	Meerut	0.7	24.0
Bulandshahar	18.9	10.3	Mirzapur	16.4	14.3
Deoria	16.1	16.1	Moradabad	19.2	14.9
Etah	15.5	17.1	Muzaffarnagar	18.2	9.5
Etawah	16.7	9.5	Pilibhit	19.5	13.3
Faizabad	18.3	14.1	Pratapgarh	17.6	12.9
Farrukhabad	14.8	10.9	Rae Bareli	16.3	14.3
Fatehpur	11.8	11.6	Rampur	14.8	18.4
Firozabad	21.2	9.2	Saharanpur	22.8	9.8
Ghaziabad	15.0	9.5	Siddharthnagar	15.0	10.0
Ghazipur	16.8	12.8	Shahjahanpur	19.5	11.6
Gonda	20.8	7.2	Sitapur	17.7	13.9
Gorakhpur	16.4	14.4	Sonbhadra	3.4	18.9
Hamirpur	18.5	12.4	Sultanpur	26.6	13.9
Hardoi	16.1	13.5	Unnao	16.3	12.6
Jalaun	15.3	10.2	Varanasi	16.8	12.0

Most districts experienced positive literacy growth in both decades, indicating a broad-based expansion of education. However, the rate of increase generally slowed during 2001–2011 compared to 1991–2001, suggesting a deceleration after initial rapid gains. The decade 1991–2001 witnessed particularly strong literacy improvements in several districts: Very high increases: Badaun (42.6%), Sultanpur (26.6%), Bareilly (26.2%), Bahraich (22.9%), Saharanpur (22.8%), Banda (22.7%), whereas Ballia(-10.0%) and Bijnor(-3.9%) show negative growth rates. This period coincides with post-1990s educational expansion, including the District Primary Education Programme (DPEP) and growing emphasis on universal elementary education. Mixed and Slower Growth during 2001–2011, typically between 9–15% shows that many districts recorded moderate but lower gains. Districts such as Agra, Allahabad, Lucknow, Mirzapur, Moradabad, and Varanasi show steady but decelerated growth. As baseline literacy levels improved, marginal gains became harder to achieve, reflecting the natural slowing associated with higher initial literacy. Districts showing reversal or negative anomalies or very low growth are: Badaun (-13.7%) in 2001–2011, Bahraich (1.9%). Some districts show sharp rebounds after weak earlier growth like Ballia (-10.0 → 38.2), Bijnor (-3.9 → 33.8), Meerut (0.7 → 24.0). Such reversals may reflect census definitional changes, migration effects, administrative corrections, differential expansion of secondary education in later years.

While scrutinizing the regional Patterns it was found that the Eastern UP districts (Azamgarh, Mau, Ballia, Ghazipur, Jaunpur) generally show consistently higher growth, especially in one of the two decades, Bundelkhand districts (Jhansi, Jalaun, Hamirpur, Banda, Lalitpur) record moderate but steady increases, indicating gradual progress, Western UP districts (Ghaziabad, Meerut, Muzaffarnagar, Saharanpur) show variable

growth, with sharper improvements during 2001–2011 in some cases. The district-level analysis of decadal literacy growth in Uttar Pradesh reveals substantial progress during 1991–2001, followed by a relative deceleration in 2001–2011. While most districts continued to improve, the magnitude of gains declined, suggesting a transition from rapid expansion to consolidation. District-specific negative growth highlight the role of migration, administrative changes, and uneven educational development.

Spatial Variations in Literacy

The average literacy of Rural Uttar Pradesh (2011) is 66%. But, there is large variation in literacy rates. Some districts like Allahabad have recorded the highest literacy rate (74.41%) in the region, as compared to neighbouring districts of Kaushambi (63.69), Fatehpur (68.69) and Pratapgarh (73.10). The coefficient of skewness (S.K) is negative i.e., -0.18 which shows that there are more districts with higher levels of literacy.

Uttar Pradesh being a large state has large variations in the levels of literacy. Previous evidences of gender literacy show that gender gap in literacy is more in the rural areas as compared to the urban areas due to restrictive access of women to occupation and labour opportunities in urban areas. In the urban areas, urbanisation, awareness and accessibility to resource and infrastructure has helped in bringing down disparity in literacy rates between males and females. Besides, the large-scale migration of educated youth, especially male from rural to urban areas in search of employment opportunities and better lifestyle and education, leads to even lower literacy rates among the females in rural areas, showing a stark gap in gender literacy in the rural areas.

The literacy levels are high in the Western and north-western districts. Vicinity to the Northern Capital Region, easier accessibility to urban regions has made it possible to some extent. Ghaziabad district has a high level of literacy due to its increasing attention to female education and overall economic development in the recent years. Also districts like Varanasi, Lucknow, Kanpur. also have high literacy due to the presence of esteemed historical educational institutions in these regions.

While female literacy is less than male literacy in all the districts, male literacy varies from 55% to 86%. The northern and north-western districts as well as districts on the east have a high rate of male literacy. While male literacy patterns follow the patterns of total literacy in spatial expression, female literacy and its pattern varies.

The map in Figure 1 depicts the spatial distribution of total literacy and male and female literacy in rural Uttar Pradesh based on Census 2011 data. Districts are classified into five literacy categories, ranging from very low (46.1–53.4%) to high (73.4–77.5%) shown by graduated colors or choropleth in the map while vertical bars indicate gender-wise literacy, with male literacy consistently higher than female literacy. The overall literacy pattern in Rural Uttar Pradesh shows that literacy in Uttar Pradesh shows moderate to low levels overall, with most districts falling in the 53.4–68.8% range. Very high literacy districts (above 73.4%) are limited and spatially concentrated in the western part, indicating uneven educational development.

Figure 1: Literacy in Uttar Pradesh, 2011

Source: prepared by the author

The bar diagrams clearly show a significant male–female literacy gap across all districts. Male literacy is consistently higher, while female literacy remains substantially lower, especially in eastern and southern districts. The gender gap is narrower in western districts and widest in eastern Uttar Pradesh, indicating stronger patriarchal norms and lower female educational participation in the east.

Western Uttar Pradesh displays comparatively higher rural literacy, particularly districts closer to Delhi NCR and Haryana, reflecting better access to education, infrastructure, and socio-economic development. Central and Bundelkhand regions show moderate literacy levels, forming a transitional belt. Eastern Uttar Pradesh (Purvanchal) largely exhibits lower literacy levels, highlighting persistent educational backwardness. Districts in eastern Uttar Pradesh and parts of Bundelkhand fall in the lowest literacy category (46.1–53.4%). These areas are characterized by high population pressure, poverty, agrarian dependence, and weak educational infrastructure.

Rural literacy in Uttar Pradesh is marked by strong spatial inequality. West–East divide is prominent: literacy declines steadily from west to east. Gender disparity remains a major concern despite overall literacy gains. The pattern reflects the combined influence of economic development, urban proximity, social structure, and government intervention effectiveness.

Figure 2: Gender Disparity in Literacy in Uttar Pradesh, 2011.

Source: prepared by the author"

The map illustrates the district-wise gender disparity in literacy in rural Uttar Pradesh for the year 2011, measured as the difference between male and female literacy rates. The districts are classified into five categories, ranging from low disparity (0.15–0.18) to very high disparity (0.26–0.29).

Gender disparity in rural literacy is widespread and significant across Uttar Pradesh. Most districts fall in the moderate to high disparity categories (0.21–0.26), indicating a persistent gap between male and female literacy.

Only a few districts show low gender disparity, suggesting limited gender equity in rural education.

Western Uttar Pradesh shows a mixed pattern. Some districts have lower to moderate disparity, reflecting relatively better female educational participation. However, pockets of high disparity still exist, particularly in the south-western parts. Central Uttar Pradesh displays comparatively lower disparity, forming a belt of relative gender balance in literacy. Eastern Uttar Pradesh exhibits high to very high gender disparity, with several districts falling in the 0.26–0.29 category, highlighting severe gender inequality. Bundelkhand region also records high disparity, reflecting socio-economic backwardness and poor access to female education.

On the basis of disparity, Uttar Pradesh can be divided into the following categories:

Very High Disparity: These include districts of Basti, Maharajganj, Deoria, Kushinagar, Sonbhadra, Mirzapur, Lalitpur. These include districts in eastern Uttar Pradesh and parts of Bundelkhand show the highest gender gaps in literacy. These regions are characterized by patriarchal social norms, early marriage, poverty, and limited schooling facilities for girls.

High Disparity: These include districts of Bahraich, Shravasti, Balrampur, Siddharthnagar, Banda, Chitrakoot, Mahoba. The districts are mainly concentrated in eastern Uttar Pradesh and Bundelkhand.

Medium Disparity: Meerut, Bulandshahr, Aligarh, Mathura, Mainpuri, Sultanpur, Jaunpur, Ghazipur are the districts included in this category. This region is spread across western,

central, and eastern UP. Female literacy is improving in these districts but still lagging behind males and represents the average rural condition of the state.

Low Disparity: Sitapur, Barabanki, Fatehpur, Etawah, Auraiya, Kannauj. It surrounds the very low disparity belt and shows a transitional zone between developed and backward regions. It also reflects gradual social change and school enrolment of girls.

Very Low Disparity: Lucknow, Kanpur Nagar, Kanpur Dehat, Unnao, Rae Bareli, Hardoi depict very low disparity of Literacy. These are located in Central part of the state. This region shows better access to education, roads and government schemes.

Gender Disparity in Literacy among different social groups

The scheduled castes and tribes being the socially backward classes show difference in disparities in gender literacy.

	SC	ST		SC	ST
Districts	disparity	disparity	Districts	disparity	disparity
Agra	0.28	0.27	Jaunpur	0.27	0.25
Aligarh	0.30	0.29	Jhansi	0.31	0.25
			Jyotiba Phule		
Allahabad	0.27	0.27	Nagar	0.28	0.30
Ambedkar Nagar	0.22	0.23	Kannauj	0.20	0.05
Auraiya	0.18	0.19	Kanpur Dehat	0.19	0.38
Azamgarh	0.24	0.22	Kanpur nagar	0.19	0.36
Badaun	0.27	0.22	Kaushambi	0.29	0.73
Baghpat	0.27	0.00	Lakhimpur Kheri	0.28	0.28
Bahraich	0.27	0.24	Kushinagar	0.24	0.25
Ballia	0.26	0.24	Lalitpur	0.29	0.29
Balrampur	0.30	0.33	Lucknow	0.21	0.22
Banda	0.28	0.38	Maharajganj	0.28	0.28
Barabanki	0.23	0.23	Mahoba	0.27	0.48
Bareilly	0.25	0.07	Mainpuri	0.21	0.19
Basti	0.24	0.23	Mathura	0.31	0.33
Bijnor	0.23	0.25	Mau	0.22	0.18
Bulandshahar	0.31	0.56	Meerut	0.23	0.31
Chandauli	0.26	0.23	Mirzapur	0.26	0.25
Chitrakoot	0.24	0.05	Moradabad	0.26	0.49
Deoria	0.27	0.26	Muzaffarnagar	0.26	0.16
Etah	0.26	0.18	Pilibhit	0.25	0.20
Etawah	0.19	0.41	Pratapgarh	0.25	0.15
Faizabad	0.23	0.12	Rae Bareli	0.24	0.26
Farrukhabad	0.23	0.42	Rampur	0.24	0.50
Fatehpur	0.24	0.40	Saharanpur	0.22	0.14
Firozabad	0.22	0.10	Shahjahanpur	0.27	0.25
Gautam Buddha			Sant Kabir		
Nagar	0.28	0.18	Nagar	0.29	0.30
			Sant Ravidas		
Ghaziabad	0.23	0.16	Nagar (Bhadohi)	0.23	0.06
Ghazipur	0.26	0.22	Shrawasti	0.28	0.28
Gonda	0.28	0.20	Siddharthnagar	0.28	0.28
Gorakhpur	0.26	0.22	Sitapur	0.24	0.31
Hamirpur	0.28	0.52	Sonbhadra	0.26	0.32
Hardoi	0.27	0.28	Sultanpur	0.25	0.23
Hathras	0.28	0.33	Unnao	0.23	0.31
Jalaun	0.27	0.18	Varanasi	0.24	0.24

SC literacy disparity shows moderate variation across districts. This indicates that SC disadvantage is widespread and fairly uniform across UP. Most districts cluster around 0.40–0.50, indicating persistent structural inequality rather than isolated pockets. Economically developed states of North and North-west have a high rate of literacy. The districts which have a low economic prosperity like Shrawasti, Bahraich, Balrampur have low literacy among the SCs. ST disparity exhibits very high inter-district variation with extremely high disparity in some districts and near absence of ST population in others (leading to 0 values). ST disadvantage is highly spatially uneven, unlike SC disparity. Districts with high ST disparity are likely areas where tribal populations are present but face severe educational exclusion, inadequate access to schooling, or socio-economic marginalisation. Bundelkhand districts (Jhansi, Hamirpur, Mahoba, Lalitpur, Chitrakoot) show moderate SC disparity, but very high ST disparity, especially in Hamirpur and Mahoba, thereby indicating acute tribal educational disadvantage in this region. Eastern UP districts (Bahraich, Balrampur, Shrawasti, Siddharthnagar) show moderate SC disparity and moderate ST disparity, reflecting mixed tribal presence and socio-economic constraints. Western UP districts (Bulandshahar, Meerut, Moradabad, Rampur) exhibit

some of the highest ST and SC disparities, possibly linked to migration patterns, urban-rural divides, and uneven access to education.

Scheduled caste and Scheduled tribes are the backward castes which have been marginalised from the mainstream development process. Uttar Pradesh has high SC and ST population of about 22.9% and 15%. Among the major SCs, Chamar and Dhobi have shown the highest literacy rate (49 per cent), while Pasi have recorded the lowest literacy rate. Similar trend has been registered for these castes in respect of female literacy also.

Conclusion

The present study highlights the persistence of pronounced spatial and social disparities in literacy in rural Uttar Pradesh over the period 1991–2011, despite substantial overall improvement in literacy levels. Rural literacy in the state increased significantly during the two decades, particularly driven by rapid gains in female literacy. This progress is reflected in the steady decline of the Gender Disparity Index from 0.52 in 1991 to 0.23 in 2011. Nevertheless, the findings clearly demonstrate that literacy growth has been uneven across districts and social groups, and gender inequality in education remains deeply entrenched.

Spatial analysis reveals a distinct west-centre-east divide in rural literacy. Western and north-western districts, benefitting from proximity to the National Capital Region, better infrastructure, and higher levels of socio-economic development, record comparatively higher literacy levels and relatively lower gender disparity. In contrast, eastern Uttar Pradesh and Bundelkhand continue to lag behind, forming persistent pockets of low literacy and very high gender disparity. The regional classification of districts into very low, low, medium, high, and very high disparity zones further underscores the concentration of severe gender inequality in eastern and southern districts, while central Uttar Pradesh emerges as a relative zone of balance.

The district-level analysis of literacy growth indicates that the most rapid improvements occurred during 1991–2001, coinciding with the expansion of primary education initiatives such as the District Primary Education Programme (DPEP). The subsequent decade (2001–2011) witnessed a relative deceleration, suggesting a transition from rapid expansion to consolidation. District-specific anomalies, including negative or highly uneven growth, point towards the influence of migration, administrative changes, and uneven implementation of educational policies.

Disparities among social groups further accentuate educational inequality. Scheduled Castes exhibit uniformly high literacy disparity across districts, reflecting long-standing structural disadvantages. Scheduled Tribes show extreme inter-district variation, with Bundelkhand and parts of eastern Uttar Pradesh experiencing acute tribal educational exclusion. These patterns indicate that social marginalisation intersects strongly with gender and spatial disadvantage, reinforcing cycles of low literacy and limited human capital formation.

Overall, the study demonstrates that while Uttar Pradesh has made measurable progress in expanding rural literacy, deep-rooted regional, gender, and social inequalities persist. Addressing these disparities requires a shift from uniform policy approaches to region-specific and group-sensitive interventions, with particular emphasis on female education in eastern Uttar Pradesh and Bundelkhand, quality improvement in primary schooling, and targeted support for Scheduled Castes and Scheduled Tribes. Without addressing these structural inequalities, further gains in literacy are likely to remain uneven and socially fragmented.

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